

DIRECTIONS D1.4:

Report on technical design constraints for electrical energy hubs

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Chapter 1

Executive summary

The large-scale integration of renewable energy, particularly offshore wind, into European power systems requires major transmission grid expansion. Electrical Energy Hubs (EEH) have emerged as a key concept: multifunctional, multi-GW nodes that aggregate offshore generation and transmit it to onshore control areas via multiple interconnections. Despite several concrete projects already being proposed (such as the Princess Elisabeth Island in Belgium and the Danish energy islands), no structured planning methodology with clear decision hierarchies has yet been established for EEH. This deliverable addresses that gap by identifying and classifying the main technical design constraints and considerations relevant to EEH planning, grouped into seven areas of interest and ranked across three criticality classes.

Hard constraints: the most binding, which must be satisfied before any further planning proceeds, relate to two areas. First, network operational security: any EEH must be designed so that the loss of any single element never exceeds the dimensioning incident of the connected synchronous area (e.g. 3 GW for continental Europe, 1.8 GW for Great Britain). Second, electricity market design: an effective market framework must ensure social welfare is maximised and all asset owners are adequately remunerated, which is particularly challenging given the multi-country nature of most EEH projects. *Main drivers:* not strictly binding at the system level, but essential for efficient and secure operation, cover four areas. Protection strategies (the choice between non-selective, partially selective, and fully selective DC fault-clearing strategies) must be co-optimised with the network layout. CAPEX and OPEX, including the high costs of offshore equipment, limited manufacturer supply for HVDC components, logistics, and the cost of increased frequency restoration reserves, must be minimised while meeting technical requirements. Future proofness and modular expandability — designing for incremental growth using standardised building blocks — is essential to avoid

sunk costs and enable multi-country meshed grids. Finally, sustainability considerations around CO₂ emissions, biodiversity impact, and societal acceptance must be embedded from the earliest planning stages. *Key considerations*: less critical to overall system control but significantly influencing final design and costs, include the choice of HVDC technology (cable configuration, converter type), electrical losses (which can represent up to 10% of lifetime CAPEX), and reliability, availability, and maintainability (RAM) analysis to maximise uptime, especially in harsh offshore environments.

The report concludes by establishing a dependency hierarchy among these areas: hard constraints drive the main drivers, which in turn shape the key considerations. This structured framework gives TSOs and asset owners a transparent, replicable basis for investment decisions, and sets the foundation for integrating these constraints into optimisation models, such as Optimal Power Flow and Transmission Network Expansion Planning, to enable more rigorous cost-benefit analyses of future grid expansion projects.

This deliverable's content is based on the following paper currently under review:

- G. Bastianel, C. Hardy, N. Charels, D. Van Hertem and H. Ergun, "Identification of Technical Design Constraints and Considerations for Transmission Grid Expansion Planning Projects", arXiv:2512.13496, 2025.

Chapter 2

Introduction

In its decarbonization plans, the European Union aims to install 450 GW of offshore wind capacity in its territory by 2050 [1]. Furthermore, the Esbjerg (2022) [2], Ostend (2023) [3] and Hamburg (2026) [4] North Sea summits pledge to install 300 GW of offshore wind capacity by 2050 in the North Sea area. An efficient transmission system design is needed to transport such amounts of power to shore in an affordable way. In this regard, High Voltage Direct Current (HVDC) links proved to be the most cost-effective means of transmitting power over long distances [5, 6]. So far, HVDC links have mainly been Point-to-Point (PtP), connecting two converters within the same synchronous area, e.g. the ALEGrO link between Belgium and Germany [7], in two different asynchronous areas, e.g. the Nemo link between Belgium and the UK [8], or to radially deliver electricity generated by a wind farm to the onshore grid, e.g. in BorWin 1 in the Netherlands [9]. Recently, the idea of using hybrid interconnectors linking two control areas with a wind farm in between them has been explored, for example, for the Nautilus project between Belgium and the UK [10] and the HansaLink between Germany and the UK [11]. With extended offshore wind projects, e.g. as the Dogger Bank wind farm in the UK [12], and growing HVDC grid projects [13, 14], the aggregation of multi-GW power capacity and interconnection to different countries has been introduced in [15] and recently proposed in *offshore energy hubs* [16] and *energy islands* projects from the Belgian (Elia) [17] and Danish (Energinet) [18] transmission system operators (TSOs), supporting the need for interconnections currently existing in the European power system [19]. Furthermore, the North Sea Wind Power Hub project proposed to create a network of islands with its hub-and-spoke concept [20]. As these projects can be proposed onshore with other types of renewable energy sources (RES) with the same technical challenges, we focus on offshore electrical energy hubs (EEHs) and their functional specifications as discussed in [21].

An EEH is defined as a “*multifunctional node in a power system, managed*

separately from the main existing control areas, aggregating local GW-size electrical generation capacity. It is characterized by a high density of electrical equipment and has multiple interconnections to existing control areas” [21]. Given the large scale of such projects [17, 22, 23], their efficient planning is crucial to maximizing both the power generation and transmission to existing control areas while guaranteeing safe and reliable operations of the entire grid. To reach these goals, this Chapter identifies and discusses the main technical constraints to be considered by TSO and asset owners during the planning stage of EEH. After this short introduction, I present a general overview of the identified technical constraints and the motivation behind this work in Section 3. Section 4 discusses each constraint related to the planning of EEH and the areas of interest to which they relate. Moreover, Section 5 classifies the constraints following a hierarchy based on their criticality for the project. They are divided into three classes, namely *hard constraints*, *main drivers*, and *key considerations*. Finally, Section 6 concludes the deliverable and describes possible future work related to the planning of EEH.

Chapter 3

Motivation and contribution

With their multi-GW size, EEH projects can positively benefit the overall socio-economic welfare of the control area where they are installed by providing large amounts of low-carbon energy. This outcome strongly depends on how efficiently EEH projects are integrated into the existing power system. For this reason, this deliverable aims to extend the findings from the “IEEE Technical report PES-TR86 - Studies for Planning HVDC” [24], which focuses on studies for planning new HVDC links to be added to existing power systems. The technical report [24] distinguishes six main phases for the transmission development process, ranging from techno-economic analyses in the early phases of the planning process to detailed engineering decisions during the actual project realization. The six phases are displayed for clarity in Figure 3.1, with this deliverable focusing on the first two.

The *first phase* establishes a transmission expansion plan where high-level capacity needs are identified using market simulations. Furthermore, bottlenecks in the existing grid are identified, usually relying on OPF simulations. Several investment options for grid expansion are determined based on the identified bottlenecks. Finally, these grid expansion options are compared using CBA methodologies based on several economic, technical, social, and environmental criteria, such as, e.g., the project of common and mutual interest in the ENTSO-e CBA [25]. The output of the first stage is usually the required capacity, location, and technology of the new investments.

The *second phase* consists of conducting feasibility studies for the chosen investment options, where the detailed technical parameters of the investments are identified. Examples are electrical parameters (voltage and current rating, number of circuits needed, impedance values, etc.), high-level substation design, protection requirements, and high-level control requirements to achieve grid connection compliance.

Due to their novelty and a lack of a coordinated master plan for grid expansion (in Europe), no clear guidelines regarding the planning of EEH have been discussed in the literature. Particularly, a hierarchy linking the main

Figure 3.1: Six main phases of the transmission expansion planning process [24]. This work identifies and discusses relevant technical constraints for investments in EEH projects, and focuses on the first *transmission expansion plan* and second *feasibility studies* phases.

technical constraints behind the initial design choices for EEH has never been proposed. Identifying such technical constraints can help transmission asset owners to streamline the EEH’ planning process and guarantee transparency in the decisions regarding their final design. In addition, these technical constraints can represent the first step toward a master plan for transmission expansion planning through EEH connecting several countries, as proposed, e.g., in the North Sea Wind Power Hub project [20] and in projects in the Mediterranean Sea [13]. For these reasons, the contributions behind this deliverable are:

- Identification of the main areas of interest to be considered by transmission asset owners when evaluating investments in EEH.
- Identification of the main technical constraints related to EEH’s planning and classification into three categories, namely *hard constraints*, *main drivers*, and *key considerations*. Based on these three categories, relations between different constraints are drawn, while they are ordered hierarchically according to their importance.
- Recommendations on how to integrate the identified technical constraints into existing optimization models, in particular for steady-state operations of hybrid AC/DC grids.

Chapter 4

Identified technical constraints

We identify seven main areas of interest related to the planning of EEH, which we show in Figure 4.1. These areas feature purely technical topics such as *network integration*, *HVDC technologies*, *future proofness & modular expandability*, and *RAM*, techno-economical ones such as *costs* (CAPEX, OPEX, and space requirements) and *electricity market design*, and one societal, *sustainability*. While EEH are transmission technology-agnostic, we include HVDC technologies among the main areas of interest. As shown in previous Figure ??, these technologies are widely adopted for transmitting power over long distances, and their use in multi-terminal and meshed grids connecting several EEH is expected to increase [26], although several technical challenges remain to be addressed. Therefore, we consider it important to devote particular attention to these technologies.

4.1 Network integration

The section is divided into two parts, namely *network operational security* and *grid reinforcements and congestion management of the existing grid*. The first includes the power system as a whole, while the latter discusses solutions to reduce grid congestion and guarantee efficient power transmission.

4.1.1 Network operational security

EEH include several GW of RES installed power capacity, of which the electricity is transmitted to control areas on the onshore grid. Given their multi-GW size, new investments in EEH should not influence the *operational security* of the power system to which they are connected, which is defined as “*the transmission system’s capability to retain a normal state or to return to a normal state as soon and as close as possible, and is characterized by thermal limits, voltage constraints, short-circuit current, frequency limits, and stability limits*”

Figure 4.1: Main areas of interest of the identified constraints related to the planning of EEH projects in the power system.

by ENTSO-e’s network code on operational security [27]. To that end, TSO apply the N-1 security criterion, which protects the power system from operation conditions leading to limit violations of the grid’s technical constraints as a result of an outage of a single grid element. To ensure the N-1 security criterion, TSO apply *remedial actions* (RA), technically defined as “..any measure applied by a TSO to maintain operational security. In particular, remedial actions serve to fulfill the (N-1) criterion and to maintain operational security limits.” [27]. Therefore, in case of a LoI in continental Europe’s power grid, several mechanisms ensure that the frequency is always within a given safe operational range. The frequency regulation mechanisms are divided into FCR, automatic FRR (aFRR), and manual FRR (mFRR). The timescale of the three mechanisms is shown in Figure 4.2.

FCR are European-wide reserves with a maximum FCR contracted capacity of 3 GW at the continental synchronous area level. With the use of UFCS for generators if the loss of power is higher than that limit [29]¹. Contrarily, in continental Europe, aFRR and mFRR mechanisms needed to be activated by the TSO of the country where the contingency takes place. Therefore, the dimensioning of the aFRR and mFRR needs to be computed by each TSO for their power system. Consequently, aFRR/mFRR reserves are dimensioned according to the effect of possible contingencies happening in a TSO’s grid. For example, expectations for the mFRR and aFRR reserves

¹The maximum allowable LoI is defined as 1.8 GW for Great Britain [30] and 1.4 GW in the Nordic power grid [31].

Figure 4.2: Division of frequency regulation with exemplary frequency curve (top) and power type responsibilities (bottom) [28].

to be adopted in Belgium are dependent on the expected increase in forecast error linked to (the ramping of) RES generation, as indicated by the “Adequacy and flexibility study for Belgium, 2026-2036” [32]: “Fast flexibility: the need for flexibility that can react within 15 minutes of real time – to cover prediction errors or generation and transmission (HVDC) asset outages – is expected to double, exceeding 3 GW in 2036.” In this regard, platforms such as PICASSO [33] and MARI [34] have been established. They aim to create platforms for the exchange of balancing energy from frequency restoration reserves with automatic activation, or aFRR-Platform (PICASSO), and future development and operation of manual activation reserves, or mFRR-platform (MARI). The main rationale behind these platforms is to increase the economic efficiency of contracting aFRR and mFRR through cross-border competition. As EEH aggregate multi-GW generation capacity and transmit the generated electricity via several interconnections to existing main control areas, several network elements can create deep frequency deviations in case of faults. These deviations can lead to a further LoI as other generation assets might disconnect due to their under-frequency protection. Consequently, both the conceptual planning of EEH and their real-time operation are constrained by the FCR requirement and the maximum allowable frequency deviation in the network. A risk assessment approach computing the available transmission capacity at any point in time by the EEH is employed by system operators.

Constraint: The grid must always be operated to avoid the presence of any contingency with an instantaneous impact larger than the dimensioning incident for the given power system, i.e. the maximum FCR level, and with a lasting impact larger than the FRR in any control area.

4.1.2 Congestion management and reinforcements of the existing grid

In the absence of enough transmission capacity to transmit power across a given transmission system, *physical congestion* takes place in the power system. Physical congestion can worsen with new considerable loads added to the grid, such as data centers, which typically desire to be connected to the power grid within a short period of time, but create further congestion due to their large demand [35]. A common, yet expensive, measure used by TSO to alleviate congestion is the redispatch of generators/loads [36]. In Germany, for example, congestion costs have approximately counted for 2.774 bn€ in 2024 alone [37, 38]. This issue goes beyond the European power grid, with, for example, congestion costs of 13.5-8.33 bn\$ in 2023 and 2024 [39, 40] for all the US Independent System Operators. Therefore, to accommodate a deeper penetration of RES generation in the power grid while maintaining the system's adequacy and security, RA through the tap changing of PST, OTS [41–43], and BuS [44–47] are getting increasing attention to optimize the grid topology at any point in time, together with methodologies to find relevant areas in the grid to be optimized [48]. Such RA fall within the extended concept of "GET", also including FACTS, dynamic line rating and HVDC interconnectors [49]. The main idea behind such GET technologies is to maximize the transmission capacity in the grid by using it more dynamically [50, 51], while waiting for effective grid expansion projects.

On the one hand, the first offshore grid expansions were built in the context of a greenfield approach, aiming to maximize the RES generation of (mainly) single offshore wind farms connected with a PtP link to the onshore grid, e.g. in [52]. With offshore EEH, the congestion of the part of the onshore grid closest to the shore becomes a compelling issue. Specifically, onshore grid reinforcements are needed to guarantee redundancy and reliability in the power transmission. In the future, with many EEH projects being proposed in areas with a limited extension, such as the North Sea area [17], thorough planning of each investment and its interconnections to other existing/proposed projects is key in maximizing the generation and transmission capacities among countries. Building transmission infrastructure in such a coordinated way results as well in a minimization of grid con-

gestion.

On the other hand, onshore EEH projects are mostly built in the context of a brownfield approach, where an efficient integration in the existing grid infrastructure is crucial. As adding GWs of capacity (and related transmission infrastructure) to the generation fleet of a power system can create undesired congestion, its resilience and redundancy need to be evaluated for a large set of operating conditions [53], e.g. with high demand hours or in case of contingencies, while taking into account all the technical [54] and societal issues [55] which might delay such projects.

For both cases mentioned above, the available hosting capacity of the existing transmission grid needs to be quantified before considering possible candidates for further transmission expansions, similar to the methods currently used in distribution grids [56]. Then, new potential transmission corridors should be identified and optimized. As advocated by [57], among its KPI, the evaluation of candidates should also include grid congestion and RES curtailment based on detailed nodal grid models, going beyond the current zonal methodology used in current studies [25, 58]. Note that the aforementioned reasoning about a more flexible utilization of the transmission grid and efficient onshore and offshore expansions are translated into several initiatives, such as the “Non-costly remedial action optimization” [59] or “Regional operational security coordination” [60] initiatives in the Core CCR mentioned in Section ??, and are relevant in the future of the European power system depicted in the EU Grids package from December 2025 [61], or in offshore grids such as the one expected to be built in the North Sea [26, 62, 63].

Consideration: Topological remedial actions and efficient grid expansion plans have the potential to reduce grid congestion. EEH are efficiently integrated into the grid by i) selecting appropriate connection points for new investments and ii) appropriately selecting grid reinforcement projects.

4.2 HVDC technologies

EEH aim to aggregate and transmit large amounts of power over long distances. Since HVDC transmission systems are cheaper than AC technologies over long distances (500-800 km for onshore connections, and ~100 km for offshore cables) [64, 65], and guarantee enhanced power flow controllability and frequency support between asynchronous zones [66], this Section briefly describes the building blocks of this technology, and refers to relevant literature on them. As introduced in Section 4.1.1, the maximum FCR level

is the main technical constraint for the network operational security of an EEH. As a result, the required number and type of HVDC cables and HVDC converters need to be selected such that the outage of a single element does not lead to a larger LoI than the maximum allowable limit. Furthermore, the protection strategy of the EEH, e.g. selectivity [67], needs to complement the chosen grid design to fulfill frequency regulation constraints, i.e., the maximum LoI.

4.2.1 HVDC cables configurations

Three main configurations of HVDC systems exist and influence the EEH's DC substation layout. Each of them includes one or two poles, with a potential ground connection and metallic return, as shown in Figure 4.3. They

Figure 4.3: Configurations and grounding for HVDC grids: (a) asymmetric monopolar, (b) symmetric monopolar, and (c) bipolar [67].

can be classified as [67]:

- **Asymmetric monopole:** the current flows through the pole at high DC voltage V_{dc} and returns via the metallic return, which is low-impedance

grounded. The configuration is shown in Figure 4.3 (a).

- **Symmetric monopole:** both poles are at high DC voltage with opposite signs $\pm V_{dc}$. The DC side is ungrounded or high-impedance grounded, and the ground connection can be given at multiple points. The configuration is shown in Figure 4.3 (b).
- **Rigid bipole:** two poles are used at high DC voltage with opposite signs $\pm V_{dc}$. The amount of power that can be transferred is increased compared to the monopoles, but only one DC side current loop exists during normal operation [68]. Therefore, the rigid bipole can only operate in balanced conditions, and a fault on one of the poles leads to the full cable being unavailable. The configuration is shown in Figure 4.3 (c), without the dotted line.
- **Full bipole:** Two poles are used at high DC voltage with opposite signs $\pm V_{dc}$. The third conductor is low-impedance grounded and is used as a DMR. Differently from the rigid bipole, full bipoles can be operated in an asymmetrical manner with different powers flowing through the two poles [69], as the DMR guarantees enhanced flexibility. This configuration is currently the standard for offshore HVDC cables set by the Dutch-German TSO TenneT with their 2GW 525 kV plan [70]. Note that this configuration is more expensive than the rigid one because of the presence of the DMR. Especially with long cables, the difference in cost can become substantial. For this reason, the benefit brought by a DMR to the system needs to be assessed to select the most cost-effective option. The configuration is shown in Figure 4.3 (c).

Note that bipoles can use the ground as a return in case of faults, while they are balanced with no ground current during normal operations. In case of fault, the current can continue to flow using the earth as a return through ground return electrodes installed at each end of the line, operating in monopolar mode. Direct ground return is often not allowed by grid codes due to its environmental impact. As a result, the DMR, although more expensive, is the preferred solution [71].

4.2.2 Modular Multilevel Converter types

This short paragraph describes the main types of converters used in HVDC systems, which were shortly introduced in previous Section ???. The content is mainly based on S. Wenig's PhD thesis [72]. I refer the reader to [72] for a thorough description of each topology.

- **VSC:** Among the different available converter types, MMC-VSC are the most efficient topology [72] as:

- They decrease or do not need AC filtering, reducing converter station space requirements.
- They can control active and reactive power independently at the AC point of common coupling.
- The modular nature of the SM in the MMC guarantees more flexible operational features by e.g. using energy storage to reduce fluctuations and AC/DC interactions.
- Unplanned maintenance actions and downtime are reduced by using redundant SM to improve the maintenance strategies.
- Lower losses occur due to the reduced switching frequency of power electronic devices.

The thermal issues created by contingencies that cannot be handled by control actions are the most dangerous to the converters. The design of the MMC-VSC converters should deal with the severity of such contingencies, selecting between HB, FB, or extended topologies.

- *LCC*: LCC-HVDC use particular transformers with on-load tap changers and different available winding configurations [73]. LCC HVDC have high current capabilities and are suitable for transferring high (> 2GW) amounts of power with good reliability and low maintenance, but they are active consumers of reactive power, due to their inductive behavior. In addition, these converters require advanced filtering and high short-circuit powers.

Therefore, large reactive power compensation installations often need to be added to LCC converter stations. Contrarily, VSC HVDC are able to inject and absorb reactive power into the grid, which allows active voltage control of the transmission grid. In addition, LCC HVDC need extended AC filtering. These reasons make VSC HVDC more suitable for offshore EEH, but LCC HVDC links are still used with onshore systems where a high amount of power needs to be transmitted radially from a remote location and with a low amount of interconnectors.

4.3 Protection strategies

ACCB are widely used to enhance the power system's redundancy, as they guarantee that a fault can be cleared in each line terminal [67]. As such, in AC systems, each network component is assigned to protection zones that selectively protect the system in case of contingencies. DCCB, on the other hand, are considerably more complex and costly [74]. As a consequence, mainly three protection strategies exist, illustrated in Figure 4.4 below.

Figure 4.4: Example fault-clearing strategies in an extended HVDC grid: (a) a nonselective fault clearing using AC circuit breakers (dc1) or fault-blocking converters (dc2), (b) a partially selective fault clearing using HVDC circuit breakers or a DC-DC converter, and (c) a fully selective fault clearing using HVDC circuit breakers [75].

- Nonselective strategy:** the entire grid is a protection zone. If a component fails in a DC grid, the entire grid, or the whole faulty pole if the grid only contains full bipoles, is brought to zero power and re-energized after the faulted component has been isolated. Common DC protection components used for this strategy are mechanical switches, such as disconnector and fast disconnector switches [67]. This strategy is commonly used by point-to-point HVDC links characterized by a limited amount of power. For DC grid power flows of several GW, a nonselective strategy might imply power imbalances higher than the e.g. European dimensioning incident of 3 GW in case of a fault. Having to almost instantaneously ramp down and up in power with a considerable power capacity would hinder the stability of the whole European grid. As such, for HVDC grids with injection points into the same synchronous area totaling more than 3 GW, a non-selective protection strategy is not feasible in the European context, also considering that the defined maximum LoI is 1.8 GW for Great Britain [30], and 1.4 GW [31] for the Nordic area, respectively.
- Fully selective strategy:** the DC grid is protected as the AC one, with DCCB protecting every HVDC link. Since DCCB are still expensive and considerably larger than ACCB, the fully selective strategy is not likely to be used for any EEH project unless strictly needed (and economically feasible).
- Partially selective strategy:** the DC grid is split into subparts which are each protected with a nonselective strategy. As a result, the impact of faults on the DC grid is limited while keeping the investment costs

for DC protections substantially lower than for the fully selective strategy. Especially two types of DC protection components are required for this strategy, namely i) mechanical switches without fault-current interruption capability within the protection zones and ii) equipment with fault-current interruption capability in the interconnections between the protection zones [67].

4.3.1 Busbar arrangements

Different protection strategies imply that the DC (and AC) busbars need to be adapted to host the protection equipment and/or be able to reconfigure their topology according to the EEH's design choice and goal. Common AC substation layouts such as the single busbar/single breaker, ring bus, breaker and a half or double busbar configurations shown in Figure 4.5 can be extended to DC grids depending on the application [67]. As mentioned earlier, the increased selectivity and redundancy eventually lead to higher investment costs. In this sense, it is important to select the most efficient protection strategy starting from the early stages of the planning process and include the costs and benefits related to the different protection strategies in the whole planning and design optimization process. Therefore, possible extensions should be foreseen in the EEH design since the beginning of the project, as the space and insulation distances needed by DC equipment are considerably higher and more expensive than for AC equipment.

Figure 4.5: An example of busbar topologies and arrangements for breakers and current-limiting inductors: (a) a single busbar/single breaker, (b) a ring bus, (c) a breaker-and-a-half scheme and a (d) double busbar [67].

Constraint: The co-optimization of the network layout and protection strategy must consider operational security constraints, such as the maximum LoI.

Consideration: The cable configuration, MMC converter type and protection strategy choice influence the maximum available power transfer of a multi-terminal DC grid. The EEH's flexibility, redundancy, and extendability should be prioritized, but case-specific arrangements depend on the project's general goal.

4.4 Costs

Given the multi-GW size and the amount of network components involved in EEH, these projects are extremely capital-intensive. For this reason, a careful assessment of the total costs and market conditions related to them is necessary to avoid sub-optimal investments.

This section elaborates on the CAPEX, OPEX, space requirements, and losses requirements in EEH. Given the current volatility of the market and uncertainty related to the technology readiness level and large-scale production of some key components, reliable cost figures are difficult to derive [54]. For this reason, we refer to relevant reports that provide indicative cost figures throughout this Section. However, it should be noted that both costs, and particularly market prices, are highly volatile at the time of writing this thesis, and might change substantially in the future.

4.4.1 CAPEX analysis and market fitness

CAPEX are the upfront costs paid by an investor to build the structure and electrical equipment of an EEH, including financial interests to be paid to the actors lending the capital. The "IEEE Technical report PES-TR86 - Studies for Planning HVDC" [24] is used as the main reference to list the main factors related to the CAPEX of an EEH.

- **Development: Planning, Consent, FEED:** FEED analyses are essential to assess a project's overall engineering-related costs. While the general best practices for budgeting large-scale (or mega) projects are extensively discussed in the literature [76, 77], some peculiar aspects related to EEH can be listed, especially when related to offshore investments. CAPEX costs for EEH vary substantially among different installations depending on several project-specific factors, such as regulatory framework, variability in cost components, TSO and regulators' involvement, optimal technical decisions, location of the installation,

etc. Additionally, separating the converter supply and civil works into different contracts increases the overall costs (if there is no abuse of market power) since both parties require manpower for activities such as project management and site supervision. When the effort needed for coordination, management, and control interfaces increases, the enhanced complexity of the project leads to more risk exposure, i.e., more costs. In addition, the lack of public data about general offshore installations increases the uncertainty around EEH and makes the benchmarking of the costs with similar projects impossible. A general rule of thumb for TSO is that the cost of physical areas/volumes (especially offshore) is the main cost component for FEED analyses. Therefore, the space occupied by equipment and the project's general offshore footprint needs to be minimized.

- **Procurement of equipment and components, market fitness:** Given the complexity of the technology, high investment costs, and highly skilled resources needed, only a handful of manufacturers can currently build HVDC cables and (VSC-MMC) converters at the moment [54]. In addition, no new entrant is expected to appear in the market soon, as the industry's investment and operational costs are extremely high. Furthermore, entering the market requires highly skilled personnel, which is currently difficult to acquire. Moreover, the low offer and increasing demand for HVDC links around the globe cause high market volatility and a push towards standardized solutions for the converter manufacturers to speed up their production and create a supply chain around them, avoiding custom-built solutions. As a result, even if the HVDC configuration and protections used in an EEH should be optimized according to the general goal of the project, there is a push towards standardization of a common solution, such as 2GW 525 kV (higher voltages are possible, such as 640 kV [78] and 800 kV [79]) HVDC bipoles with DMR [70], which can lead to a lower price for this configuration even if they involve more components and conductors.
- **Logistics and installation:** The installation costs of EEH are directly related to the location of the project and the existing infrastructure around it. Parameters such as the types of soil, recurrence of heavy storms, presence of wildlife in the area, harsh weather conditions, limited physical accessibility, etc., increase the project's total costs. While a general rule of thumb is that the more remote an installation is from the load centers, the higher the installation costs would be, offshore investments tend to be the most expensive, especially when in deep waters with limited accessibility due to constant strong winds around them. Onshore investments have lower installation costs, but their public ac-

ceptance is extremely low, as the population dislikes overhead lines (more) and cables (less) passing close to their properties [55]. In this sense, the practical installation of HVDC cables and possible obstacles on the designed route are influencing the overall costs. Moreover, particular attention should be paid to laying the cables in areas with rocks, volcanic phenomena, etc. [80], as damaging the cable leads to substantial delays in the commissioning of the projects.

Onshore projects are logistically more easily accessible than offshore ones, as the latter requires several boats to carry the equipment and build the EEH offshore. In the case of offshore wind, building the construction facilities on the coast next to a harbor assures that the wind turbines and electrical equipment are delivered to the EEH location more easily. Nevertheless, the weather conditions of the area need to be studied to find possible windows in which the equipment can be installed safely.

- **Interest During Construction:** Typically, interest rates are related to the inherent risk of the project. A reliable timing of the project is necessary to avoid delays, which lead to considerably higher interest at the end of the project, i.e. additional investment costs.

Note that recent European system studies, such as the Elia blueprint for 2050 [81], include in their scenarios HVDC investment overnight costs in the range of 1680–3800 €₂₀₂₂/MW/km for onshore links and of 1680–3000 €₂₀₂₂/MW/km for offshore links. Regarding the AC/DC converter station costs, the onshore costs range is 250–325 M€₂₀₂₂/GW, while the offshore one is 550–700 M€₂₀₂₂/GW, including the offshore platform required to hold the converter. The cost of other (expectedly expensive) components, such as DCCB, remains highly uncertain, as these technologies are not yet deployed in the European system. It should be noted, however, that these estimates are subject to significant uncertainty due to the current market volatility, and future cost levels may deviate substantially from the reported ranges.

Consideration: An EEH should meet its power aggregation and transmission goals at the lowest possible cost while meeting the existing technical and space requirements.

4.4.2 OPEX analysis

OPEX are costs related to the daily operations of an EEH and, in general, to all the operational expenses during its lifetime that were not included in the

CAPEX assessment. Two OPEX-related categories from [24] can be applied to the context of EEH:

- **Designed lifetime:** given the significant investment costs, EEH are expected to operate for several decades. For example, the Princess Elisabeth Belgian energy island [17]’s structure is built with a 100-year time horizon. As the electrical installations have a considerably lower lifetime, the substations and converter stations are supposed to last for at least 40 years [82]. The auxiliary low-voltage equipment has instead lower requirements, such as 16-20 years, being easier to replace and less expensive. Additional reinforcements to the EEH’s structure should be foreseen for critical elements located in extreme conditions and difficult to replace, such as high-voltage offshore transformers. In such cases, a trade-off needs to be made between a more robust and thus expensive design (CAPEX) and more recurrent maintenance (OPEX).
- **Cost of unplanned and planned maintenance actions:** every unplanned maintenance action results in an economic loss due to the reduction of power transfer through the EEH, as the installations are unmanned and need to be available 24/7. The repair time of such faults might be increased by harsh weather conditions, especially for offshore projects, due to the difficulty of reaching the installation in adverse weather conditions. Spare components of key elements should therefore be foreseen on the EEH. Similarly, maintenance periods need to be optimally planned to minimize the out-of-service hours. In this sense, choosing highly reliable systems, i.e., with low failure rates, reduces the mean time to repair and increases the availability of the overall project, as discussed later in the deliverable in Section 4.7.
- **Cost of FRR increase:** even if the most impactful incident of an EEH can be lower or equal to the dimensioning incident (FCR of the connected grids), its impact can be higher than the LoI or loss of load resulting from any other incidents within a control area. As such, the integration of an EEH into a control area can lead to the system operator having to purchase more mFRR and/or aFRR services. The cost difference between the frequency restoration reserves that have to be purchased by a system operator with and without considering the EEH can be attributed to the EEH as OPEX costs. Depending on the cost to increase these reserves, it could be better to limit the capacity of the EEH.

Consideration: The designed lifetime and planned maintenance actions are design parameters depending on the characteristics of the EEH. The (potential) unavailability of the project should be minimized by organizing effective planned maintenance actions and investing in reliable components, especially if the EEH is placed in harsh weather conditions.

The capacity of the EEH can lead to increases in the required frequency restoration reserves. These reserves need to be considered in the OPEX estimates of a candidate project and might influence the EEH's optimal capacity.

4.4.3 Space requirements

As previously mentioned, the cost of the equipment offshore is the main component of the investment costs for offshore installations. When considering building new EEH, three main categories of projects can be identified from the space requirements perspective. According to each category, different design constraints are applied to a new EEH project.

- **Construction of an EEH with limited surface area:** the total surface area of the EEH is fixed because of space limitations given by, e.g., existing infrastructure, nature reserves, or political borders. The EEH design choices must satisfy the requirements for generation and transmission capacity without exceeding the space limits.
- **Construction of an EEH with limited installed generation and/or transmission capacity:** the capacity of the EEH is constrained because of limitations in the total generation and/or transmission capacity that can be installed. The focus is on achieving the grid functions expected by the project. Nevertheless, the total surface area, i.e., the investment costs, should always be minimized.
- **Construction of an EEH with no limited surface area and capacity constraints:** the EEH's design can be optimized without pre-existing limitations regarding its area or installed capacity. The EEH's design is optimized according to the project's overarching goal discussed during its planning stages.

Based on the Belgian [17] and Danish [18, 23] proposed EEH projects, we distinguish six main building blocks and their respective components. Note that the dimensions of the elements are taken from publicly available sources [83] and are related to components that have yet to reach maturity in most of the cases. While the dimensions of each network component can

be different depending on each manufacturer, an estimate of the dimension ratios between the several components is displayed in Fig. 4.7. For new EEH projects, the dimensions of the different building blocks can be used as input for a knapsack problem [84] aimed at installing the best combination of EEH's building blocks based on the requirements of a maximum power capacity for a given space or minimizing the EEH space for a given power capacity.

- **Wind collection:** collection point of the AC cables transferring power from the OWF to the EEH and AC infrastructure to raise the AC MV from the OWF (32 kV, 66 kV or possibly 132 kV in the future) to HV through a transformer. Additional elements that can be present in this building block are AC Pre-Insertion Resistor (AC-PIR), AC harmonic filters, and AC switchgear. According to [83], the AC substation for the collection of the wind farm has a dimension of roughly 580 m², while the MV/HV transformer 128 m² is 4.5 times smaller.
- **HVDC converter and cable:** VSC-MMC 525 kV converters are proposed to be the standard for offshore HVDC cables. These converters need the AC voltage to be in the range of 250-300 kV. An HV/HV transformer is therefore required to increase the AC voltage to the desired level. Additionally, the converter might require DC-PIR [85], DC braking system [86], DC reactor [87], and DC cable discharge [88] devices depending on the project. The HVDC cables for offshore transmission in the future, based on TenneT's 2 GW plan [70], are expected to have a DMR. Furthermore, the converters are the largest electrical component. Depending on the manufacturer, their valve halls have dimensions of roughly 32 m x 59 m x 18 m for the 500 kV MMC base case and 25 m x 45 x 12 m for the 100 kV MMC with parallel arms and MMC in parallel [89]. According to [83], the whole converter occupies an area of roughly 2250 m², with the HV/HV transformer being 128 m².
- **AC substation and cable:** for installations close to shore such as the Princess Elisabeth energy island [17], AC cables can still be used to transfer the power onshore. Before the AC cable, the voltage from the OWF collection points needs to be increased to 220 kV with an MV/HV transformer which is estimated to have the same length and width as the HV/HV transformer [83]. The AC substation, mentioned previously in the section, has an estimated area of 580 m². As a comparison, existing AC 220 kV platforms in the Baltic and North Seas have a surface of 51 m x 31 m (1581 m²) and a height of 35 m for the Baltic Eagle 476 MW offshore wind farm [90], and a surface of 58 m x 32 m (1856 m²) and a height of 26 m for the 700 MW Borssele

offshore wind farm [91]. Examples of equipment in the AC substation are AC switchgear, AC harmonic filters, AC protections, and AC-PIR.

- **AC coupler:** AC coupling equipment is used to connect and disconnect part of the EEH via AC switchgear, similarly to what is shown on the left-hand side of Figure 4.6. While the AC coupling is useful for

Figure 4.6: Hybrid hub solution from [83] in which AC (left) or DC (right) coupling is possible.

rearranging the AC busbar topologies of an EEH, the space required for these installations is trivial compared to other parts of the project.

- **DC coupler:** DC switching units are used to DC-couple different HVDC cables in an EEH, as shown on the right-hand side of Figure 4.6. The network components being used are the same as the ones mentioned in the “expansions” part of the section but, in this case, only the DC switchgear is considered. The same reflections about the DC protection strategies and space needed for the equipment are valid for this point.
- **Expansions:** Eventual expansions towards other EEH control zones need to be considered in the EEH’s original plan. For example, the first multi-terminal VSC HVDC grid in Europe, the Caithness Moray

Shetland project, was designed to allow further expansion in the point of coupling of its terminals [92]. Depending on the chosen DC protection strategy and the EEH's operations in conjunction with the overall system, possible DC protections include DCCB or DC disconnectors.

On the one hand, with a DCCB, a DC fault can be interrupted at any point in time, and the faulted line is isolated without power loss in the other DC lines [93].

On the other hand, using DC disconnectors implies that the power through the entire DC grid needs to be brought to zero in case of a DC fault, with a nonselective protection strategy. Afterwards, the faulted line is removed, and power is transferred again through the DC grid.

Since DCCB are expensive and large network components, the DC-preventive decoupling strategy [94, 95] has been proposed to avoid their use in small DC grids, and it has been techno-economically evaluated against DCCB in [96]. Following this strategy, a given DC system is decoupled without loss of power into several zones when the total power flowing through the DC grid is above the dimensioning incident discussed in Section 4.1.1. Nevertheless, the maximum amount of power that can be transferred during the DC grid is reduced.

The operator of the EEH must therefore choose between a more robust DCCB or a preventive DC-side decoupling strategy with DC disconnectors, which results in less power being transferred but smaller and less expensive equipment, as [83] reports the DCCB to occupy about 400 m², while DC disconnectors are significantly smaller. Note that for more extended MTDC grids, the DCCB is arguably the preferred choice to guarantee the secure operations of the power system.

Consideration: The maximum dimensions of the different building blocks of an EEH are used to select the best combination of network components for a given space or power capacity.

4.4.4 Losses

Electrical losses are a typical design requirement from TSO to the components' manufacturers. Following the Joule losses' law $P_l = R \cdot I^2$, there has been a tendency to reach higher voltage levels and lower currents in the last decades. The main technical constraint related to losses is the safe evacuation of the heat coming from the key electrical components. As methods to compute the losses for e.g. cables and MMC converters are well known [97],

Figure 4.7: Main building blocks of an EEH. The ratio between the areas of the components are based on realistic data from [83].

each component should be designed to operate safely in a given temperature range for most of its lifetime, being able to control the amount of losses while the cooling equipment prevents it from overheating. From the techno-economic perspective, power losses can be a significant cost factor as the losses are accumulated over the lifetime of the assets of several decades. In this respect, the costs associated with power losses for HVDC systems can be in the order of 10 % of the total expected CAPEX accumulated over the lifetime of the asset, as computed in [98] for a 300 MW offshore wind connected via VSC HVDC to the onshore system.

Therefore, it is beneficial to investigate trade-offs between the cost of measures for reducing system losses and the anticipated costs for losses themselves. As an example, using submarine cables with higher cross-sections inherently will lead to higher CAPEX of equipment due to the increased use of copper or aluminum, as well as higher installation costs due to the cable weight. However, such costs might be justified if the lifetime loss reduction due to the higher cross-section is economically acceptable.

Consideration: The losses in the system are a design choice for system operators. They can account for some percentage of the total investment-related costs over the project's lifetime.

4.5 Electricity market design

While discussing different market mechanisms is beyond the scope of this thesis, electricity market designs are briefly discussed in this Section, as they turn out to be one of the most relevant parameters for the effective implementation of grid expansion planning projects. In fact, the choice of the market design in which the EEH are operated has a large influence on the benefits to the socio-economic welfare brought by the EEH [99]. When proposing a market design, four properties of market-clearing mechanisms are desired [100–102]:

- **Market efficiency:** In an efficient market, the overarching principle of an efficient market design is the maximization of social welfare. After the market is cleared, no market player desires to unilaterally deviate from its outcomes.
- **Incentive compatibility:** No market player imposes their market power and everyone offers their products at their marginal cost without strategic behaviors.
- **Cost recovery:** Every market player's operational profit is positive and every operational cost is recovered.
- **Revenue adequacy:** The market operator never experiences a financial deficit. For example, in power systems, the revenues for the generators are always higher or equal to the costs paid by the generators. The market is "budget balance" if the market operator has no financial deficit nor excess, i.e. the revenues of the generators are equal to the costs paid by the loads.

In the context of EEH, the overarching goal is to minimize the cost for society while guaranteeing that the owners of the generation assets are remunerated for their investments. Therefore, the market design decision should consider the interests of as many stakeholders as possible to select the most efficient design according to the final goal of the EEH project. In addition, EEH and HVDC links in general are extremely capital-intensive projects, but will likely benefit more than one system operator, especially in locations like the European North Sea. Based on this fact, and due to the fragmented nature of the European power system from a system operator perspective, the first regulations for creating cost- and benefit-sharing have been put forward by the European Commission [103, 104]. Specifically in the North Sea, the OTC [62] investigates the possibility of a "Joint Regional Cost Sharing" [105], intending to involve the parties sharing the costs in the offshore

grid planning and cost-sharing stage, and to provide a transparent cost-sharing decision providing the right remuneration for all the involved parties, also through the use of metrics, e.g. ex-ante metrics (prior to any final investment decision), ex-post metrics (after a final investment decision) or a combination of the two. While the interested reader is referred to [105] and ongoing work from the OTC for a comprehensive description of methodologies to allocate costs and benefits among different stakeholders, it is worth emphasizing that such initiatives are instrumental in refining existing approaches to identifying system needs [106]. As such, they are expected to play a key role in determining the future expansion of the European power system.

Consideration: An effective market design minimizes the cost for society while guaranteeing that the owners of the generation and transmission assets are remunerated for their investments.

4.6 Future proofness & modular expandability

4.6.1 Expandability

Expandability aims to ensure that both predictable and unpredictable future developments can be integrated into a system with minimal adaptations to the already existing infrastructure. While expandability should be enabled at marginal additional costs, minimizing prior investments benefits the economic feasibility of an EEH. Therefore, from a system perspective, developers need to find the optimal design to avoid sunk costs while making sure “no regret” investment decisions are identified and executed on time.

4.6.2 Achieving modular expandability

As introduced in Section 4.4.1, the standardization of HVDC technologies helps manufacturers speed up their production and create a supply chain around their key network components. As a result of this standardization, modular EEH can be established following the building blocks listed in Section 4.4.3. The benefits brought by modular expansions [107] in EEH are:

- Economy of scale and optimized supply chain, resulting in faster construction and delivery times [108].
- Enhanced flexibility of the whole project.

- Avoidance of sunk costs due to i) production inefficiencies, ii) unknowns due to limited knowledge of sensible information, and iii) non-efficient planning for ad-hoc solutions.
- Steady incremental growth.

Among the benefits, the avoidance of sunk costs is often overlooked. While production inefficiencies and non-efficient planning are general issues, the effective expansion of planned MTDC projects depends on the ability of components supplied by multiple vendors to be compatible and work together under varying operational modes, defined as “interoperability” [109, 110]. Without agreements on key interoperability topics, the design process is challenging due to both technical reasons, e.g. difficulties in predicting and ensuring the stable integration of components without experiencing interactions or incompatibilities, as well as organizational. The reader is referred to [109, 110] for a thorough explanation of the interoperability issue in hybrid AC/DC grids. Moreover, EEH’ expandability depends mainly on the location where the project is built. In the North Sea case, the political agreements between the North Sea countries, the high capacity factors from offshore wind, and the lack of pre-existing infrastructure between the countries make it the ideal case to foresee further connections to other EEH. If an EEH is in a smaller and more isolated area far from other control areas, the interconnection will most likely be a PtP HVDC link. Therefore, we identify the following drivers for EEH’s expandability:

- Presence of existing infrastructure in the same area as the EEH.
- Physical location
- Agreements with other control areas
- RES capacity factors in the area

Optimization models can be developed to ensure that the EEH’s building blocks occupy the lowest area possible while achieving the project’s goal. The co-design of planning, operations, control, and protection of MTDC grids is advised to maximize the integration of RES in the existing power system. When future extensions are considered, feasibility studies such as OPF simulations, EMT studies, and fault analyses should be performed to guarantee the safe and reliable operations of the EEH and the already existing grid as a whole. The output of these studies might result in requirements for some network components such as, e.g., converter fault-ride through and multi-vendor interoperability.

Consideration: Expandability is one of EEH' key purposes for the power grid of the future. It consists of the integration of adequate provisions for interface facilitation in the system design. A balance between the controlled costs of prior investments and those of later uncertain developments needs to be found to achieve economic efficiency.

4.7 Reliability-Availability-Maintainability

As all the network elements in a power system, EEH are subject to failures and other unpredictable events that have the potential to make them partly or fully unavailable for a certain period of time, dependent on the type of fault.

On the one hand, RAM computes an inherent trade-off between the simplicity of a system that needs to remain as lean as possible to limit the probability of occurrence of undesirable events.

On the other hand, the application of the right level of subdivision and integration of redundancy limits the impact of such fault events. As such, RAM is an overall system optimization problem that balances the three main features:

- **Reliability**, defined as *“the probability of a device or system performing its purpose adequately for the time intended under the operating conditions encountered”* [111]. Reliability is linked to two main aspects, adequacy and security.
 - Adequacy, or static reliability, is the ability to ensure that there is enough generation and transmission capacity to meet the demand in a given power system.
 - Security, or dynamic reliability, is the ability to ensure that a given power system is resilient against abrupt disturbances, such as faults, short circuits or loss of components.
- **Availability**, measuring the probability of a given network component to function in a given period. As a rule of thumb, the lower the curtailment of the rated capacity, the higher the system availability.
- **Maintainability** refers to the *“Measures taken during the development, design, and installation of a manufactured product that reduce required maintenance, manhours, tools, logistic cost, skill levels, and facilities, and ensure*

that the product meets the requirements for its intended use” [112]. Indicatively, the higher the subdivision, redundancy, and accessibility of the system, the higher its maintainability.

Consideration: The availability of EEH heavily influences their benefits to the socio-economic welfare and thus needs to be maximized within the boundaries of reasonable capital expenditures. It is a natural balance between system simplicity and integrated redundancy.

4.8 Sustainability

EEH are by definition key enablers of asset rationalization and lead to the reduction of CO_2 emissions through the transmission of sustainable electricity. Nevertheless, the impact of such major infrastructure on the environment is substantial. They thus require additional efforts to mitigate negative impacts and provide support and preservation to nature for a sustainable environment. Sustainability is promoted through diverse laws and regulations to which asset owners need to comply. As such, permitting procedures integrate strong requirements related to environmental impact assessment [113]. In addition, direct financial incentives also further reinforce efforts towards carbon neutrality. Sustainability measures can be clustered into 3 main domains of action: climate, biodiversity, and societal:

- **Climate:** CO_2 emissions are present from the planning to the decommissioning of an EEH project. These emissions need to be tracked transparently, reduced to the maximum extent, and compensated. The most impactful and traceable activities concern equipment production, transport, and installation. First, the amounts of material and, more specifically, of metals are to be minimized. As such, preference goes towards technologies offering the highest electricity transport capacity per unit of total equipment weight. For HVDC systems of a specific rating, different technologies may exist and their climate impact assessment will likely require a trade-off between the voltage level and the current for:
 - The converter stations, in which structural quantities play a major role and directly depend on insulation distances, i.e. voltage levels.
 - The HVDC cable system, in which metal conductor quantities can amount to very large figures, especially for very long interconnectors, depends on its current rating.

Second, the energy consumption and emissions types during the construction of EEH are related to the amount of necessary work and the means to perform these operations. Ensuring minimization of transport and installation works, together with the use of adapted machinery whose own climate impact throughout its life cycle is the lowest available on the market, are relevant indicators of a positive climate approach. Third, the use of gas-insulated high-voltage equipment to reduce the footprint of converter stations has to be treated cautiously. In the frame of the phase-out of the fluorinated greenhouse gases [114], the use of SF_6 as the most mature gas insulating technology currently continues to represent a risk of large additional emissions to be balanced with its associated space gains and positive impact on the number of structural materials. Lastly, the overall power losses (mostly by heat dissipation in electrical resistances) can add up to significant figures in the overall lifetime of an EEH project. Therefore, they must not be neglected when assessing the overall climate impacts of the proposed solutions, as mentioned in previous Section 4.4.4.

- **Nature and Biodiversity:** in addition to the global climate impacts, sustainable projects should consider their influence on direct natural surroundings. Existing and future fauna and flora can in fact be considerably impacted by the new infrastructure and related construction works. In practice, a set of preliminary studies focused on nature inclusion and promotion of biodiversity should be performed to identify the necessary measures early on and plan for these to reach a *nature-inclusive design* boosting the ecological and environmental value from the start of the project [115]. Among others, the following levers represent primary focus aspects that can have a considerable influence on the wildlife in the EEH region:
 - **Cable routing:** selection of appropriate cable routes, bundling strategy, trench design and burial depth.
 - **Offshore structural elements:** selection of appropriate foundations location, materials and design characteristics.
 - **The use of hazardous products:** limitation and mitigation of leaks and spills of harmful products such as oils, heavy metals or other chemicals.

Even though a nature-inclusive design and project planning are fundamental, specific monitoring throughout the entire process is necessary, as well as a proper decommissioning strategy at the end of the asset's life cycle. This ensures that the parts of the EEH are treated following the circular economy's rules and best practices [116].

- **Society:** EEH are developed in the general interest of society. Their practical implementation should as such also consider the perspective of the exposed public in the direct vicinity of the new assets. In addition, the well-being of the construction and operation workers involved in the various stages of the project, i.e. engineering, manufacturing, transport and installation, operation, etc., should always be considered as a priority. Among others, audible noise and electromagnetic fields in the low as well as high-frequency ranges are consecutive emissions emanating from (parts of) the electrical infrastructures. Their realistic anticipation during the design stage, detailed monitoring during the production process, and final on-site verification during commissioning and trial operation consist of the main part of the environmental impact assessment of the project. Moreover, proximity sourcing reduces the amount of transport work with direct climate impact, while promoting the local industry and creating an additional common sense of purpose for the population. Therefore, the asset owners need to plan for clear and transparent public communications from the very start of the project to ensure an open dialogue with the community and mutual understanding.

Consideration: A sustainable EEH requires minimization of its associated CO_2 emissions, in-depth comprehension and willingness to support the surrounding natural habitat, together with empathy towards the vast community of direct and indirect project participants and stakeholders.

Chapter 5

Discussion

Throughout the previous Sections, we discussed several areas of interest to consider when evaluating investments in EEH, or, more generally, grid expansion planning projects. For each area, we identified the main technical design constraints and considerations to be addressed during the planning of such projects. Table 5.1 includes a summary of all the identified technical design constraints and considerations per area, while classifying each area in three different criticality classes, namely *hard constraints*, *main drivers*, and *key considerations*. Even though all the technical design constraints and considerations need to be fulfilled to advance the planning process of an EEH, *hard constraints* are the most critical for system operators and must be fulfilled before proceeding with the further stages of the planning of an EEH. *Main drivers* are related to the overall operation and control philosophy of an EEH. Different from the *hard constraints*, they are not binding from the system perspective but are key for the efficient and secure use of the EEH. Moreover, *key considerations* are related to the design parameters of different network components. While they are arguably less relevant to the overall control of a power system, they can considerably influence the final design of an EEH or the financial investments related to it. Thus, they should not be underestimated. Constraints and considerations referred to the network operational security, grid reinforcements, congestion management (Section 4.1.1) and electricity market design (Section 4.5) are classified as *hard constraints*. EEH protection strategies (Section 4.3), space requirements (Section 4.4.3), CAPEX and market fitness (Section 4.4.1), OPEX (Section 4.4.2), future proofness and modular expandability (Section 4.6) and environmental and ecological impact-related technical design constraints and considerations (Section 4.8) are categorized as *main drivers*. Finally, constraints related to the selection of the needed HVDC technology (Section 4.2), losses requirements (Section 4.4.4), and RAM analysis (Section 4.7) fall within the *key considerations*.

In addition, Fig. 5.1 depicts the hierarchy between the different areas of

interest identified in this work. Starting from the *hard constraints* on top, the dependencies between the different areas, and therefore related identified constraints and considerations, are represented through arrows to the *main drivers*, and subsequently to the *key considerations*.

Figure 5.1: Dependencies between the different relevant areas of interest for the identified technical constraints and considerations for the planning of investments in EEH and, more generally, grid expansion projects. Based on our classification in three different criticality classes, namely *hard constraints*, *main drivers*, and *key considerations*, the arrows link the most stringent constraints and considerations, the *hard constraints*, to the *main drivers*, related to the overall operation and control philosophy of an EEH. Subsequently, the *main drivers* are linked to the *key considerations*, related to the design parameters of the different network components.

Table 5.1: Classification of the identified technical design constraints and considerations for considering investments in EEH and, more generally, grid expansion planning projects according to three different criticality classes, namely *hard constraints*, *main drivers*, and *key considerations*. *Hard constraints* are the most critical for system operators. *Main drivers* are related to the overall operation and control philosophy of an EEH. Different from the *hard constraints*, they are not binding from the system perspective but are key for the efficient and secure use of the EEH. *Key considerations* relate to the design parameters of different network components. Even if less relevant to the overall control of a power system, they can considerably influence the final design of an EEH.

Identified technical constraint/consideration	Area of interest	Description of the technical constraint/consideration	Constraint/consideration criticality
Network operational security	Network integration	The grid must always be operated to avoid the presence of any contingency with an instantaneous impact larger than the dimensioning incident for the given power system, i.e. the maximum FCR level, and with a lasting impact larger than the FRR in any control area.	Hard constraints
Grid reinforcements and congestion management	Network integration	Topological remedial actions and efficient grid expansion have plans the potential to reduce grid congestion. EEHs are efficiently integrated into the grid by i) selecting appropriate connection points for new investments and ii) appropriately selecting grid reinforcement projects.	Hard constraints
Electricity market design	Electricity market design	An effective market design minimizes the cost for society while guaranteeing that the owners of the generation and transmission assets are remunerated for their investments.	Hard constraints
Protection strategies	HVDC technologies	The co-optimization of the network layout and protection strategy must consider operational security constraints, such as the maximum loss of infeed.	Main drivers
Space requirements	Costs	The maximum dimensions of the different building blocks of an EEH are used to select the best combination of network components for a given space or power capacity.	Main drivers
CAPEX and market fitness	Costs	An EEH should meet its power aggregation and transmission goals at the lowest possible cost while meeting the existing technical and space requirements.	Main drivers
OPEX	Costs	The designed lifetime and planned maintenance actions are design parameters depending on the characteristics of the EEH. The (potential) unavailability of the project should be minimized by organizing effective planned maintenance actions and investing in reliable components, especially if the EEH is placed in harsh weather conditions. The EEH capacity can lead to increases in the required frequency restoration reserves. These need to be considered in the OPEX estimates of a candidate project and might influence the EEH's optimal capacity.	Main drivers
Future proofness and modular expandability	Future proofness and modular expandability	Expandability is one of EEHs' key purposes for the power grid of the future. It consists of the integration of adequate provisions for interface facilitation in the system design. A balance between the controlled costs of prior investments and those of later uncertain developments needs to be found to achieve economic efficiency.	Main drivers
Environmental and ecological impacts	Sustainability	A sustainable EEH requires minimization of its associated CO ₂ emissions, in-depth comprehension and willingness to support the surrounding natural habitat, together with empathy towards the vast community of direct and indirect project participants and stakeholders.	Main drivers
Cable configuration, converter type and busbar arrangement	HVDC technologies	The cable configuration, MMC converter type and protection strategy choice influences the maximum available power transfer of a multi-terminal MT DC grid. The EEH's flexibility, redundancy, and extendability should be prioritized, but case-specific arrangements depend on the project's general goal.	Key considerations
Losses Requirements	Losses	The losses in the system are a design choice for system operators. They can account for some percentage of the total investment-related costs over the project's lifetime.	Key considerations
RAM analysis	Reliability Availability Maintainability	The availability of EEHs heavily influences their benefits to the socioeconomic welfare and thus needs to be maximized within the boundaries of reasonable capital expenditures. It is a natural balance between system simplicity and integrated redundancy.	Key considerations

5. DISCUSSION

Chapter 6

Conclusion and future work

This paper aimed to identify the most relevant technical design constraints and considerations when considering investments in EEH, and more generally, transmission grid expansion planning projects. We identified several areas of interest for such constraints and considerations, namely *network integration, HVDC technologies, costs, electricity market design, future proofness & modular expandability, RAM, and sustainability*. Each area of interest is discussed separately throughout the paper. Furthermore, the relevant constraints and considerations are divided into three main criticality classes according to their importance in the EEH planning process, namely *hard constraints, main drivers, and key considerations*. Based on this classification, we assign each identified area of interest to a class and derive the dependencies among all the areas of interest. Future work will deal with including the identified constraints in mathematical optimization models used for evaluating the economic benefit brought by an EEH to the overall society, such as OPF simulations and TNEP problems. By including the identified constraints in such models, cost-benefit analyses taking into account the physical constraints of power systems can be proposed, and the effectiveness of grid expansion projects can be more precisely quantified. In addition, a more transparent and unified methodology for transmission grid expansion planning projects can be developed based on the findings of this deliverable, which could lead to reduced delays in the planning and construction of new projects, reducing the renewable energy curtailment due to such delays.

Bibliography

- [1] European Council, Council of the European Union, *European Green Deal*, [Online] Available: <https://www.consilium.europa.eu/en/policies/green-deal>. (accessed March 8, 2024).
- [2] Governments of the countries in the North Sea area, *The Esbjerg Declaration: A Greener and More Sustainable Europe*, [Online] Available: <https://esbjerg.eu/the-esbjerg-declaration>. (accessed March 2, 2026), 18 May 2022.
- [3] Ostend Declaration of Energy Ministers, *The north seas as Europe's green power plant delivering cross-border projects and anchoring the renewable offshore industry in Europe*, 2023.
- [4] Governments of the countries in the North Sea area, *The Hamburg declaration - Building the North Seas' power hub for a resilient and competitive Europe*, [Online] Available: <https://tinyurl.com/4tyfrbjj>. (accessed March 2, 2026), 26 January 2026.
- [5] D. Van Hertem, O. Gomis-Bellmunt, and J. Liang, *HVDC grids for transmission of electrical energy: Offshore grids and a future supergrid*. IEEE Press, 2016.
- [6] S. Hardy, D. Van Hertem, and H. Ergun, "A techno-economic analysis of meshed topologies of offshore wind hvac transmission," in *2021 IEEE Madrid PowerTech*, 2021, pp. 1–6. doi: 10.1109/PowerTech46648.2021.9494784.
- [7] ENTSO-e, *Project 92 - ALEGrO*, [Online] Available: <https://eepublic-downloads.entsoe.eu/clean-documents/tyndp-documents/TYNDP%202016/projects/P00> (accessed March 23, 2026).
- [8] Nemolink, *Nemo Link - Interconnected to the heart of Europe's electricity market*, [Online] Available: <https://www.nemolink.co.uk>. (accessed March 23, 2026).
- [9] TenneT, *Borwin 1*, [Online] Available: <https://www.tennet.eu/projects/borwin1>. (accessed April 14, 2026).

- [10] Elia group, *Nautilus*, [Online] Available: <https://www.elia.be/en/infrastructure-and-projects/infrastructure-projects/nautilus>. (accessed March 27, 2026).
- [11] WindGrid, *WindGrid Projects Recognised in ENTSO-E's Ten-Year Network Development Plan 2026*, [Online] Available: https://www.windgrid.com/en/news/2026/03/20260305_windgrid-projects-recognised-in-entso-e-tyndp-2026. (accessed April 14, 2026).
- [12] SSE Renewables, *Dogger Bank wind farm*, [Online] Available: <https://www.sserenewables.com/offshore-wind/projects/dogger-bank/> (accessed March 27, 2026), 2026.
- [13] G. Bastianel, H. Ergun, and D. Van Hertem, "A Multi-GW Energy Hub for Southern Europe: the Mediterranean Energy Island Proposal," in *2023 AEIT HVDC International Conference (AEIT HVDC)*, 2023, pp. 1–6. DOI: 10.1109/AEITHVDC58550.2023.10179006.
- [14] Terna, *The hypergrid project and development requirements*, [Online] Available: https://download.terna.it/terna/2023_Hypergrid_project_and_development_requirements_8db79602cedc732.pdf (accessed March 27, 2026), 2023.
- [15] M. van der Meijden, "Future north sea infrastructure based on dogger bank modular island," in *15th Wind Integration Workshop (WIW)*, Vienna, Austria, 2016.
- [16] A. Lüth and D. Keles, "Risks, strategies, and benefits of offshore energy hubs: A literature-based survey," *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, vol. 203, p. 114761, 2024, ISSN: 1364-0321. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2024.114761>. [Online]. Available: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1364032124004878>.
- [17] Elia Group, *The Princess Elisabeth Island*, [Online] Available: <https://www.elia.be/en/infrastructure-and-projects/infrastructure-projects/princess-elisabeth-island>. (accessed February 27, 2026).
- [18] Danish Energy Agency, *Denmark's energy islands*, [Online] Available: <https://ens.dk/en/our-responsibilities/offshore-wind-power/denmarks-energy-islands>. (accessed February 14, 2024).
- [19] European Commission, JRC, *The interconnection needs of the european electricity system - investigations for 2030 and 2040 using metis*, [Online] Available: <https://publications.jrc.ec.europa.eu/repository/handle/JRC143965?mode=fulltext> (accessed March 27, 2026), 2025.
- [20] North Sea Wind Power Hub, *Key concepts for realizing the potential of offshore wind*, [Online] Available: <https://northseawindpowerhub.eu/key-concepts>. (accessed April 22, 2026).

- [21] G. Bastianel et al., "Review, definition and challenges of electrical energy hubs," *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, vol. 226, p. 116 258, 2026, ISSN: 1364-0321. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2025.116258>. [Online]. Available: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1364032125009311>.
- [22] Danish Energy Agency, *Energy Island in the North Sea*, [Online] Available: <https://ens.dk/en/energy-sources/offshore-wind-power/denmarks-energy-islands>. (accessed April 14, 2026).
- [23] Danish Energy Agency, *Bornholm energy island*, [Online] Available: <https://ens.dk/en/our-responsibilities/onshore-wind-power/bornholm-energy-island>. (accessed February 14, 2026).
- [24] IEEE Power & Energy Society, *Technical report PES-TR86 - Studies for Planning HVDC*, 2021. DOI: [doi/10.17023/ps0n-aq05](https://doi.org/10.17023/ps0n-aq05).
- [25] ENTSO-E, *4th entso-e guideline for cost-benefit analysis of grid development projects*, [Online] Available: <https://tyndp.entsoe.eu/resources/guideline-for-cost-benefit-analysis-4.0>. (accessed April 22, 2026).
- [26] ENTSO-e, *European offshore network transmission infrastructure needs*, [Online] Available: <https://www.entsoe.eu/outlooks/offshore-hub/tyndp-ondp/>. (accessed March 6, 2026).
- [27] ENTSO-e, *Network Code on Operational Security*, [Online] Available: https://www.entsoe.eu/network_codes/os/ (accessed August 9, 2024), 2013.
- [28] J. Figgenger et al., "The influence of frequency containment reserve flexibilization on the economics of electric vehicle fleet operation," *Journal of Energy Storage*, vol. 53, p. 105 138, 2022, ISSN: 2352-152X. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.est.2022.105138>. [Online]. Available: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2352152X22011392>.
- [29] ENTSO-e, *Task Force Overfrequency Control Schemes - Recommendations for the Synchronous Area of Continental Europe*, [Online] Available: <https://www.entsoe.eu/documents/> (accessed August 9, 2024), 2017.
- [30] National Energy System Operators, *Security and quality of supply standard*, [Online] Available at: <https://www.neso.energy/industry-information/codes>. 2025.
- [31] ENTSO-E, *Requirement for minimum inertia in the nordic power system*, [Online] Available at: https://eepublicdownloads.blob.core.windows.net/public-cdncontainer/cleandocuments/SOC%20documents/Nordic/2024/2023_-_Requirement_for_minimum_inertia_in_the_Nordic_power_system.pdf, 2023.

- [32] Elia Group, *Adequacy and flexibility study for Belgium*, [Online] Available: <https://issuu.com/eliagroup/docs>. (accessed 26 October, 2024).
- [33] ENTSO-E, *PICASSO*, [Online] Available: https://www.entsoe.eu/network_codes/eb/picasso/. (accessed August 5, 2025), 2025.
- [34] MARI - European mFRR platform, *MARI - KPI REPORT 2022-2023*, [Online] Available: https://www.entsoe.eu/documents/nc/NC%20EB/2024/MARI_report_2022_2023.pdf (accessed August 9, 2024), 2024.
- [35] International Energy Agency, *Energy and AI*, [Online] Available: <https://iea.blob.core.windows.net/assets/de9dea13-b07d-42c5-a398-d1b3ae17d866/EnergyandAI.pdf>. (accessed March 26, 2026), 2026.
- [36] G. Thomassen, A. Fuhrmanek, R. Cadenovic, D. Pozo Camara, and S. Vitiello, *Future-proofing the European power market redispatch and congestion management*, [Online] Available: <https://www.ffe.de/en/publications/congestion-management-redispatch-2-0-in-international-comparison/>. (accessed February 20, 2025), 2024.
- [37] ENTSO-e transparency platform, *Costs of congestion management*, [Online] Available: <https://transparency.entsoe.eu/congestion-management>. (accessed February 27, 2026).
- [38] SMARD.de, *Congestion management*, [Online] Available: <https://www.smard.de/page/article/5790/214060/congestion-management> (accessed February 27, 2026), 2025.
- [39] N. Shreve, J. Selker, Z. Zimmerman, and R. Gramlich, *2023 transmission congestion report*, [Online] Available: https://gridstrategiesllc.com/wp-content/uploads/Grid-Strategies_2023-Transmission-Congestion-Report.pdf (accessed July 6, 2025), 2024.
- [40] N. Shreve, J. Selker, Z. Zimmerman, and R. Doying, *Transmission congestion for 2024*, [Online] Available: https://gridstrategiesllc.com/wp-content/uploads/GS_Transmission-Congestion-for-2024.pdf (accessed February 11, 2026), 2025.
- [41] E. B. Fisher, R. P. O'Neill, and M. C. Ferris, "Optimal transmission switching," *IEEE Transactions on Power Systems*, vol. 23, no. 3, pp. 1346–1355, 2008. DOI: 10.1109/TPWRS.2008.922256.
- [42] K. Hedman, R. O'Neill, E. Fisher, and S. Oren, "Optimal transmission switching with contingency analysis," in *IEEE PES General Meeting*, 2010. DOI: 10.1109/PES.2010.5589437.
- [43] K. W. Hedman, R. P. O'Neill, E. B. Fisher, and S. S. Oren, "Optimal transmission switching—sensitivity analysis and extensions," *IEEE Transactions on Power Systems*, vol. 23, no. 3, pp. 1469–1479, 2008. DOI: 10.1109/TPWRS.2008.926411.

- [44] M. Heidarifar, P. Andrianesis, P. Ruiz, M. C. Caramanis, and I. C. Paschalidis, "An optimal transmission line switching and bus splitting heuristic incorporating AC and N-1 contingency constraints," *International Journal of Electrical Power & Energy Systems*, vol. 133, p. 107 278, 2021, ISSN: 0142-0615. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijepes.2021.107278>.
- [45] B. Morsy, A. Hinneck, D. Pozo, and J. Bialek, "Security constrained OPF utilizing substation reconfiguration and busbar splitting," *EPSR*, vol. 212, p. 108 507, 2022, ISSN: 0378-7796. DOI: [10.1016/j.epsr.2022.108507](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.epsr.2022.108507).
- [46] G. Bastianel, M. Vanin, D. Van Hertem, and H. Ergun, "Optimal transmission switching and busbar splitting in hybrid ac/dc grids," *Sustainable Energy, Grids and Networks*, vol. 46, p. 102 182, 2026, ISSN: 2352-4677. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.segan.2026.102182>. [Online]. Available: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2352467726000640>.
- [47] G. Bastianel, D. Van Hertem, H. Ergun, and L. Roald, "Day-ahead transmission grid topology optimization considering renewable energy sources' uncertainty," *International Journal of Electrical Power & Energy Systems*, vol. 174, p. 111 527, 2026. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijepes.2025.111527>.
- [48] G. Bastianel, D. V. Hertem, H. Ergun, and L. Roald, *Identifying best candidates for busbar splitting*, arXiv:2510.13000, 2025. arXiv: 2510.13000 [eess.SY].
- [49] O. Mirzapour, X. Rui, and M. Sahraei-Ardakani, "Grid-enhancing technologies: Progress, challenges, and future research directions," *Electric Power Systems Research*, vol. 230, p. 110 304, 2024, ISSN: 0378-7796. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.epsr.2024.110304>. [Online]. Available: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0378779624001925>.
- [50] EPRI, *Transmission Topology Optimization, State-of-the-Art White Paper: A GET SET White Paper*, [Online] Available: <https://www.epri.com/research> (accessed July 6, 2025), 2025.
- [51] WATT Coalition, *Unlock power by reshaping the grid topology optimization*, [Online] Available: <https://watt-transmission.org/about-transmission-topology-optimization/> (accessed January 19, 2026), 2025.
- [52] TenneT, *Alpha Ventus*, [Online] Available: <https://www.tennet.eu/projects/alpha-ventus>. (accessed July 9, 2024).

- [53] Y. Lin, Z. Bie, and A. Qiu, "A review of key strategies in realizing power system resilience," *Global Energy Interconnection*, vol. 1, no. 1, pp. 70–78, 2018, ISSN: 2096-5117. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.14171/j.2096-5117.gei.2018.01.009>. [Online]. Available: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2096511718300094>.
- [54] International Energy Agency, *Building the future transmission grid - strategies to navigate supply chain challenges*, [Online] Available: <https://www.iea.org/reports/building-the-future-transmission-grid>. (accessed April 1, 2026), 2025.
- [55] M. Neukirch, "Grinding the grid: Contextualizing protest networks against energy transmission projects in southern germany," *Energy Research & Social Science*, vol. 69, p. 101 585, 2020, ISSN: 2214-6296. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2020.101585>.
- [56] S. M. Ismael, S. H. Abdel Aleem, A. Y. Abdelaziz, and A. F. Zobaa, "State-of-the-art of hosting capacity in modern power systems with distributed generation," *Renewable Energy*, vol. 130, pp. 1002–1020, 2019, ISSN: 0960-1481. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.renene.2018.07.008>. [Online]. Available: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0960148118307936>.
- [57] O. Antoine et al., *AC/DC hybrid grid modelling enabling a high share of renewables – Final report*. European Commission and Directorate-General for Energy. Publications Office of the European Union, 2023. DOI: [doi/10.2833/627100](https://doi.org/10.2833/627100).
- [58] ENTSO-e, *About the long-term network development study*, [Online] Available: <https://tyndp.entsoe.eu/about>. (accessed April 1, 2026).
- [59] CCR Core TSO Cooperation, *Explanatory document to the Core Capacity Calculation Region methodology for common provisions for regional operational security coordination in accordance with Article 76 of Commission Regulation (EU) 2017/1485*, [Online] Available: <https://tinyurl.com/4cm279y9>. (accessed February 25, 2026), 2019.
- [60] European Commission, *Commission Regulation (EU) 2017/1485 of 2 August 2017 establishing a guideline on electricity transmission system operation (Text with EEA relevance.)* [Online] Available: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2017/1485/oj/eng> (accessed April 16, 2026).
- [61] European Commission, *Communication on the European Grids Package*, [Online] Available: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:52025C0001> (accessed February 25, 2026), 2025.
- [62] Offshore TSO Collaboration, *Expert paper II, Unlocking the potential of the North Seas Offshore TSO Collaboration*, [Online] Available: <https://tinyurl.com/ma3b3r>. (accessed March 26, 2026).

- [63] Offshore TSO Collaboration, *Expert paper III, Joint Planning in Europe's Northern Seas Supporting Europe's energy security and competitive growth through a regional approach to offshore grid development*, [Online] Available: <https://tinyurl.com/4uk9tt64>. (accessed March 26, 2026).
- [64] D. Van Hertem, O. Gomis-Bellmunt, and J. Liang, *HVDC grids for transmission of electrical energy: Offshore grids and a future supergrid*. IEEE Press, 2016.
- [65] S. Hardy, D. Van Hertem, and H. Ergun, "A techno-economic analysis of meshed topologies of offshore wind hvac transmission," in *2021 IEEE Madrid PowerTech*, 2021, pp. 1–6. DOI: 10.1109/PowerTech46648.2021.9494784.
- [66] D. Van Hertem and M. Ghandhari, "Multi-terminal VSC HVDC for the European supergrid: Obstacles," *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, vol. 14, no. 9, pp. 3156–3163, 9 2010, ISSN: 13640321. DOI: 10.1016/j.rser.2010.07.068.
- [67] D. Van Hertem et al., "Substations for Future HVDC Grids: Equipment and Configurations for Connection of HVDC Network Elements," *IEEE Power and Energy Magazine*, vol. 17, no. 4, pp. 56–66, 2019. DOI: 10.1109/MPE.2019.2909006.
- [68] C. Hirsching, M. Goertz, S. Wenig, S. Beckler, M. Suriyah, and T. Leibfried, "On control and balancing of rigid bipolar mmc-hvdc links enabling subsystem-independent power transfer," *Electric Power Systems Research*, vol. 189, p. 106768, 2020, ISSN: 0378-7796. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.epsr.2020.106768>. [Online]. Available: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S037877962030571X>.
- [69] C. K. Jat, J. Dave, D. Van Hertem, and H. Ergun, "Hybrid ac/dc opf model for unbalanced operation of bipolar hvdc grids," *IEEE Transactions on Power Systems*, vol. 39, no. 3, pp. 4987–4997, 2024. DOI: 10.1109/TPWRS.2023.3329345.
- [70] TenneT, *2 GW program*, [Online] Available: <https://www.tennet.eu/about-tennet/innovations/2gw-program>. (accessed February 27, 2026).
- [71] ENTSO-e, *Hvdc links in system operations*, [Online] Available: <https://www.entsoe.eu/Documents/2024>.
- [72] S. Wenig, "Potential of bipolar full-bridge mmc-hvdc transmission for link and overlay grid applications," 37.06.01; LK 01, Ph.D. dissertation, Karlsruher Institut für Technologie (KIT), 2019, 189 pp. DOI: 10.5445/IR/1000096294.

- [73] O. E. Oni, I. E. Davidson, and K. N. Mbangula, "A review of lcc-hvdc and vsc-hvdc technologies and applications," in *2016 IEEE 16th International Conference on Environment and Electrical Engineering (EEEIC)*, 2016, pp. 1–7. DOI: 10.1109/EEEIC.2016.7555677.
- [74] T. Erfan, R. Hamid, J. Shahram, and G. G., "Circuit breakers in hvdc systems: State-of-the-art review and future trends," *Protection and Control of Modern Power Systems*, vol. 8, no. 38, 2023.
- [75] W. Leterme, I. Jahn, P. Ruffing, K. Sharifabadi, and D. Van Hertem, "Designing for high-voltage dc grid protection: Fault clearing strategies and protection algorithms," *IEEE Power and Energy Magazine*, vol. 17, no. 3, pp. 73–81, 2019. DOI: 10.1109/MPE.2019.2897188.
- [76] B. Flyvbjerg, "Five misunderstandings about case study research," *Qualitative Inquiry*, vol. 12, pp. 219–245, 2006.
- [77] B. Flyvbjerg, N. Bruzelius, and W. Rothengatter, *Five misunderstandings about case study research*. Cambridge University Press, 2003.
- [78] M. Jeroense, P. Bergelin, T. Quis, A. Abbasi, H. Rapp, and L. Wang, "Fully qualified 640 kv underground extruded dc cable system," *CI-GRE Paris Session 2018*, 2018.
- [79] D. Zhang, M. Haeusler, H. Rao, C. Shang, and T. Shang, "Converter station design of the ± 800 kv uhvdc project yunnan-guangdong," 2008.
- [80] J. Sherwood et al., "Installation and operational effects of a hvdc submarine cable in a continental shelf setting: Bass strait, australia," *Journal of Ocean Engineering and Science*, vol. 1, no. 4, pp. 337–353, 2016, ISSN: 2468-0133. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.joes.2016.10.001>.
- [81] Elia Transmission Belgium, *Belgian electricity system blueprint for 2035-2050*, [Online] Available: https://www.elia.be/en/newsroom/2024/09/20240924_elia_publishes-blueprint-for-the-belgian-electricity-system-2035-2050 (accessed March 27, 2026), 2024.
- [82] European Eirgrid, *Offshore substation general requirements functional specification*, [Online] Available: <https://cms.eirgrid.ie/sites/default/files/publications/OFS-OSP-130-R2-Offshore-Substation-General-Requirements.pdf>. (accessed March 27, 2026), 2022.
- [83] D. Muller and et al., *Offshore energy hubs feasibility assessment of hub topologies*, [Online] Available: <https://offshoreenergyhubs.eu/index.php/2024/03/19/energy-hubsfeasibility-assessment-of-hub-topologies/> (accessed April 22, 2026), 2024.

- [84] K. Dudziński and S. Walukiewicz, "Exact methods for the knapsack problem and its generalizations," *European Journal of Operational Research*, vol. 28, no. 1, pp. 3–21, 1987, ISSN: 0377-2217. DOI: [https://doi.org/10.1016/0377-2217\(87\)90165-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/0377-2217(87)90165-2).
- [85] L. He, "Effects of pre-insertion resistor on energization of mmc-hvdc stations," in *2017 IEEE Power & Energy Society General Meeting*, 2017, pp. 1–5. DOI: 10.1109/PESGM.2017.8273916.
- [86] S. Cao et al., "Energy dissipation of mmc-hvdc based onshore wind power integration system with fb-dbs and dccb," *IET Renewable Power Generation*, vol. 14, no. 2, pp. 222–230, 2020. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1049/iet-rpg.2019.0491>.
- [87] E. Kontos and P. Bauer, "Reactor design for dc fault ride-through in mmc-based multi-terminal hvdc grids," in *2016 IEEE 2nd Annual Southern Power Electronics Conference (SPEC)*, 2016, pp. 1–6. DOI: 10.1109/SPEC.2016.7846039.
- [88] R. Ghosh, P. Seri, and G. Montanari, "Partial discharge measurements and life estimation in dc electrical insulation during voltage transients and steady state," *Electric Power Systems Research*, vol. 194, p. 107 117, 2021, ISSN: 0378-7796. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.epsr.2021.107117>.
- [89] S. Neira, P. Judge, S. Sajedi, and E. Hodge, "Converter station configurations for gw-scale mvdc systems using superconducting cables," IET, Tech. Rep., 2024.
- [90] Iberdrola, *Baltic Eagle Offshore Wind Farm - Explanatory Report*, [Online] Available: https://sgavmst.dk/media/5vec1yga/baltic-eagle_explanatory-report_rev-7_2020-11-04.pdf. (accessed March 27, 2026).
- [91] Rijkswaterstaat - Ministry of Infrastructure and Water Management, *Borssele wind farm zone*, [Online] Available: <https://noordzeeloket.nl/en/functions-use/offshore-energy-transition/offshore-wind-energy/free-passage-shared-use/borssele-wind-farm-zone/> (accessed April 13, 2026), 2026.
- [92] Hitachi Energy, *Caithness Moray HVDC Link*, [Online] Available: <https://www.ssen-transmission.co.uk/projects/project-map/caithness—moray/>. (accessed February 27, 2026), 2024.
- [93] M. Abedrabbo, "Continuous Operation of Meshed HVDC Grids During DC Faults - HVDC Circuit Breaker Integration & Design from a System Perspective," Ph.D. dissertation, KU Leuven, 2021.

- [94] P. Düllmann et al., "Preventive DC-side decoupling: a control and operation concept to limit the impact of DC faults in offshore multi-terminal HVDC systems," in *19th International Conference on AC and DC Power Transmission (ACDC 2023)*, 2023, pp. 30–37. doi: 10.1049/icp.2023.1304.
- [95] P. Düllmann et al., "Preventive DC-side decoupling: A system integrity protection scheme to limit the impact of DC faults in offshore multi-terminal HVDC systems," *IET Generation, Transmission & Distribution*, 2024. doi: 10.1049/gtd2.13214.
- [96] M. Van Deyck, G. Bastianel, G. Chaffey, H. Ergun, and D. Van Hertem, "Techno-economic comparison of preventive DC-side decoupling and DC circuit breakers in multiterminal offshore HVDC grids," *IET Conference Proceedings*, vol. 2025, pp. 137–144, 6 2025. doi: 10.1049/icp.2025.1196.
- [97] A. António-Ferreira and O. Gomis-Bellmunt, "Modular multilevel converter losses model for hvdc applications," *Electric Power Systems Research*, vol. 146, pp. 80–94, 2017, issn: 0378-7796. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.epsr.2017.01.010>. [Online]. Available: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S037877961730010X>.
- [98] H. Ergun, B. Rawn, R. Belmans, and D. Van Hertem, "Optimization of transmission technology and routes for pan-european electricity highways considering spatial aspects," in *2015 IEEE Eindhoven PowerTech*, 2015. doi: 10.1109/PTC.2015.7232638.
- [99] S. Hardy, A. Themelis, K. Yamamoto, H. Ergun, and D. Van Hertem, "Optimal grid layouts for hybrid offshore assets in the north sea under different market designs," *IEEE Transactions on Energy Markets, Policy and Regulation*, vol. 1, no. 4, pp. 468–479, 2023. doi: 10.1109/TEMPR.2023.3289582.
- [100] L. Hurwicz, "On informationally decentralized systems," *Decision and Organization*, 1972.
- [101] A. Ratha, J. Kazempour, A. Virag, and P. Pinson, "Exploring market properties of policy-based reserve procurement for power systems," in *2019 IEEE 58th Conference on Decision and Control (CDC)*, 2019, pp. 7498–7505. doi: 10.1109/CDC40024.2019.9029777.
- [102] L. Mitridati, J. Kazempour, and P. Pinson, "Design and game-theoretic analysis of community-based market mechanisms in heat and electricity systems," *Omega*, vol. 99, p. 102177, 2021, issn: 0305-0483. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.omega.2019.102177>.

- [103] European Commission Regulation, *Regulation (EU) 2022/869 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 30 May 2022 on guidelines for trans-European energy infrastructure, amending Regulations (EC) No 715/2009, (EU) 2019/942 and (EU) 2019/943 and Directives 2009/73/EC and (EU) 2019/944, and repealing Regulation (EU) No 347/2013*, [Online] Available: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2022/869/oj/eng> (accessed March 27, 2026).
- [104] European Commission Communication, *Regulation (EU) 2022/869 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 30 May 2022 on guidelines for trans-European energy infrastructure, amending Regulations (EC) No 715/2009, (EU) 2019/942 and (EU) 2019/943 and Directives 2009/73/EC and (EU) 2019/944, and repealing Regulation (EU) No 347/2013*, [Online] Available: https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=OJ:C_202404 (accessed March 27, 2026).
- [105] Offshore TSO Collaboration, *Expert Paper IV, Offshore TSO Collaboration Balancing costs, benefits and risks*, [Online] Available: <https://tinyurl.com/nvt57de2>. (accessed March 26, 2026).
- [106] ENTSO-e, *ENTSO-e releases Public Consultation on the System Needs Methodology*, [Online] Available: <https://www.entsoe.eu/news/2026/02/26/ENTSO-e-releases-public-consultation-on-the-system-needs-methodology/>. (accessed March 27, 2026), 2026.
- [107] J. K. Gershenson, G. J. Prasad, and Y. Zhang, "Product modularity: Definitions and benefits," *Journal of Engineering Design*, vol. 14, no. 3, pp. 295–313, 2003. doi: 10.1080/0954482031000091068.
- [108] World Economic Forum, *From blueprint to reality: A stronger business case for shared energy infrastructure*, [Online] Available: <https://www.weforum.org/publications/>. (accessed March 27, 2026), 2026.
- [109] G. Dawson and C. T. Nieuwenhout, *Deliverable 4.2 Multi-Part Cooperation Framework-Preliminary draft with focus on information sharing*, [Online] Available: <https://interopera.eu/publications/> (accessed April 22, 2026), 2023.
- [110] M. Wang, W. Leterme, G. Chaffey, J. Beerten, and D. Van Hertem, "Multi-vendor interoperability in HVDC grid protection: State-of-the-art and challenges ahead," *IET Generation, Transmission & Distribution*, vol. 15, no. 15, pp. 2153–2175, 2021.
- [111] C. R. Heising and R. J. Ringlee, "Prediction of reliability and availability of hvdc valve and hvdc terminal," *IEEE Transactions on Power Apparatus and Systems*, vol. PAS-89, no. 4, pp. 619–624, 1970. doi: 10.1109/TPAS.1970.292608.

- [112] B. S. Dhillon, *Engineering Maintainability*. Gulf Publishing Company, 1999.
- [113] BVG Associates, *Guide to an offshore wind farm - update 2025*, [Online] Available: <https://guidetoanoffshorewindfarm.com/wp-content/uploads/2025/06/BVGA-16464-Fixed-Guide-rF.pdf>. (accessed March 27, 2026), 2025.
- [114] European Parliament and of the Council, *Regulation (EU) No 517/2014 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 16 April 2014 on fluorinated greenhouse gases and repealing Regulation (EC) No 842/2006*, [Online] Available: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2014/517/oj/eng> (accessed March 23, 2026).
- [115] Elia, *Princess Elisabeth energy island*, [Online] Available: <https://www.elia.be/en/infrastructure-projects/princess-elisabeth-island> (accessed August 9, 2024), 2024.
- [116] E. H. Arruda, R. A. P. B. Melatto, W. Levy, and D. de Melo Conti, "Circular economy: A brief literature review (2015–2020)," *Sustainable Operations and Computers*, vol. 2, pp. 79–86, 2021, ISSN: 2666-4127. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.susoc.2021.05.001>.

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